

Medical Evaluation of Robotic Surgery Methods; A Review Study

Hoseinali Danesh^{1,2}, Javad Rahmati^{3, 4}, Mahdieh Khodabandeh⁵, Seyed
Mohammadhossein Hemadi⁶, Alireza Bahmani^{7®}

¹Plastic, Reconstructive & Aesthetic Surgeon, Assistant Professor of Zahedan University of
Medical Sciences (ZAUMS)

²Clinical Immunology Research Center at Zahedan University of Medical Sciences,
ZahedanIran

Email: drdaneshha@yahoo.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-0385-2597

³Associate Professor of Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery, IKHC, Medicine Faculty, Tehran
University of Medical Science, Tehran, Iran

⁴Department of Plastic & Reconstructive surgery, Razi Hospital, Medicine Faculty, Tehran
University of Medical Science, Tehran, Iran

Email: J.rahmati46@gmail.com

⁵Master Student of Internal Surgery Nursing, Kashan University of Medical Sciences,
Kashan, Iran

Email: mahdiehkhodabandeh1995@gmail.com

⁶Board of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Iran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran,
Iran

Email: Dr_hemadi@yahoo.com

⁷Department of Emergency medicine ,Ali Ibn AbitalebHospital,Zahedan university of
Medical Sciences,Zahedan.Orcid: 0000-0003-2690-9784

Email: alirezabahmani19831@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: Alireza Bahmani Department of Emergency medicine ,Ali Ibn
AbitalebHospital,Zahedan university of Medical Sciences,Zahedan.Orcid: 0000-0003-
2690-9784

Corresponder Email :

Email: alirezabahmani19831@gmail.com

Abstract

Along with the advances in medical science, surgical methods have also undergone many advances. Today, with the advancement of technology in all fields, including medicine, robots have entered the medical science. These robots have many uses as well as advantages and disadvantages that they enjoy in Iran and other countries. In this study, it was addressed. This study is a review of robotic surgery methods in Iran and other countries in the form of a review

study. This study is a conceptual review. The steps performed are: 1- Designing a research question, 2- Searching and extracting research-related studies, 3- Selecting related studies, 4- Tabulating and summarizing information and data, and 5- Reporting results. The results showed that robotic surgery in operations such as brain, kidney, open heart, liver, eye, laparoscopy, dental surgery, coronary artery surgery, hysterectomy, lymphadenectomy, general surgery, obstetrics, head and neck, shelf Chest, urology, endoscopy, colonoscopy, ear, nose and throat are used and have advantages such as three-dimensional vision, flexible rotation of the instrument, reduction of surgeon hand vibration with vibration filter, ease of surgery and the ability to create the required patterns. It reduces the volume of blood lost during surgery, the length of stay in the hospital, the amount of pain, and subsequently the number of analgesic doses consumed in the postoperative ward.

Disadvantages include the relative increase in operating time, the high cost of robots, and the physician's lack of sensory perception of the patient's environment.

Keywords: Robotic Surgery, Surgery, Robotics

Introduction

From the past until now, surgery has been known as a treatment for some diseases, but it was performed due to its many limited complications. Along with the advances in medical science, surgical methods have also undergone many advances (1). In traditional surgery, the surgeon has to make larger incisions to perform the surgery and damage a large amount of tissue in the patient's body. This increases the likelihood of surgical complications such as pain, bleeding, infection, and prolongs the patient's recovery time (2-5). Given the problems that exist in open surgery, surgeons have sought to minimize harm to the patient by creating new tools. This led to the emergence of a new approach called minimally invasive surgery. (Figure 1))7-6(

Figure 1. Robotic Surgery

Today, with the advancement of technology in all fields, including medicine, robots have entered the medical science. In medical science, surgery and operations in which robots are directly or indirectly involved are called "robotic surgery" (8). Robotic surgery is performed by making several small incisions in which the surgeon is able to be present without the patient's bedside and remotely while having three-dimensional vision by controlling the robot arms that

have a range of motion similar to human hands and wrists and around Are placed on the operating table to perform surgery (Figure 2) (9). Today, robots have become a very useful tool to help doctors, and their irreplaceable role in medical science is increasing every day. That's why the US National Institutes of Health has significantly increased research funding. The NIH budget for this project for 5 years is \$ 2.3 million (10). The difference between a robot and a human is not negligible in many ways. Robotic surgery, compared to traditional surgery, results in smaller incisions, increased accuracy, flexibility, better visual control, reduced pain and wounds, which leads to less time spent in the hospital. And recovery time is faster.)11(

Figure 2. A Review of Camera Viewpoint Automation in Robotic and Laparoscopic

Among the benefits of robotic surgery can be; Reduction of long recovery period after surgery, reduction of postoperative pain, reduction of the possibility of postoperative infection, reduction of hospitalization time, no need to break the sternum and open the chest in open surgeries, rapid healing of wounds, in the availability of certified surgeons with unique capabilities in more locations, greater accuracy, elimination of surgeon hand vibration, continuous and 24-hour operation 24 hours a day without fatigue. In addition to having many benefits, according to robotic surgery studies (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The evolution of robotic surgery: surgical and anaesthetic aspects

Disadvantages including; Increasing the distance between doctor and patient, reducing the speed of communication with equipment and monitors, increasing the possibility of cutting the wrong place, the possibility of disconnecting the surgeon from the operating room, low network

security and the possibility of hacking communication, patients' reluctance to use this equipment and technology, Expensive robots, lack of assistance for the doctor, lack of sensory perception of the patient's environment by the doctor. Many operations by surgical robots such as brain surgery, kidney, open heart, liver, eye, laparoscopy, dental surgery, Coronary artery surgery, hysterectomy, lymphadenectomy, general surgery, obstetrics, head and neck, chest, urology, endoscopy, colonoscopy, ear, throat and nose have been successfully performed.)¹⁰(The high accuracy of some surgical robots makes it possible to perform very difficult surgeries such as vitreoretinal surgery and eye vitrectomy in a favorable manner (12). There are several types of surgical robots. One of them is Heartlander, which is known as the smallest surgical robot in the world. Zeus robot is another robot. The other robot is the Da Vinci robot, which is known as the best robotic surgery system in the world and is made by a single commanding company. The system was approved by the US food and drug administration in 2000. In the meantime, other countries have also started working. In Iran, Sina robot surgeon (Da Vinci's rival), which was developed by researchers at Tehran University of Science in collaboration with researchers at Sharif University of Technology. Its unique feature compared to the Da Vinci robot is that it measures the force applied to the patient's body and transmits it to the surgeon through the surgical console, and its price is estimated to be one third of the American version.)¹⁰ (Although we are facing the development of surgical robots around the world, a review of scientific products in the field of surgical robots shows that the United States, China, and Japan are the three leading countries in this field, respectively, and Iran is in 15th place. The trend of scientific production in this field has started since 1990 and has been moving forward with a gentle slope and has gone through an upward trend since 2001. This trend has continued upward with fluctuations in different years. The results indicate that. There are few scientific developments in this field and few countries, universities, authors and publications have addressed this issue (13) (Figure 4). According to studies, efforts should be made to recognizeThe right requirements make it possible to use robotic surgery worldwide (14). Therefore, this study aims to investigate robotic surgery methods in Iran and other countries in the form of a review study.

Figure 4. Robot-Assisted Kidney Surgery Results Similar to Those of Traditional Methods

Method

This study is a conceptual review. The steps performed are: 1- Designing a research question, 2- Searching and extracting research-related studies, 3- Selecting related studies, 4- Tabulating and summarizing information and data, and 5- Reporting its results.

Search and extraction of research-related studies

First, articles were researched by researchers. Researchers first extracted related keywords using the MeSH strategy. Search for resources using the keywords robotic surgery, surgery, robotics, robot surgeon in Persian databases Barekat, Iran Medex, Irandoc, Magiran, SID and using the English keywords tele surgery, Robotic surgery, in Google scholar databases, Scopus, science direct, PubMed, web of science were conducted from 2013 to 2021 in October and November 1400. These words were searched separately and also as a combination of two words together using Boolean operators. In order to increase the validity of the study findings and control the bias in data entry, the search process, selection of studies and decision-making on entering or constructing the study and evaluation of the full text of the articles were performed by two independent browsers. This process was overseen by a third party.

Inclusion criteria include all articles that have examined robotic surgery and their full text is available and written in Persian and English. Exclusion criteria were studies unrelated to the title.

Extracting articles according to inclusion criteria

Using the above keywords at the end of the search, including 37 articles from Persian databases and 105718 articles from international databases and a total of 105755 studies were collected. The studies were reviewed based on inclusion criteria. The selection of related studies was done in such a way that first a list of titles and abstracts of all articles in databases is prepared by researchers. And if after reading the title and abstract, it was not possible to make a decision about the study, the full text was studied. Then, the related articles entered the research process independently and finally 43 articles were included in the study.

Figure 5. The schematic method

Tabulating and summarizing information and data

At this stage, after the data has been extracted, all study data will be summarized based on the name of the first author, year, place, title, tools or research elements in the relevant table.

Table 1: Studies Related to the Research Topic

Table 1: Studies Related to the Research Topic						
findings	Research tools	type of study	Title	Place	Year	the writer

The results of measuring and recording the time required to start the robot, ease of working with the robot, the quality of the robot in response to the surgeon's instructions, the accuracy of the robot's movements, the robot's ability to provide full image coverage, no shaking or shaking image, indefatigability Robot in long surgeries, lack of unwanted movements and lack of errors in movements indicate the safety and efficiency of the robot and its satisfactory performance during surgery.	Intervention	Experimental	Clinical evaluation of a new camera-preserving robot in laparoscopic surgery preliminary results	Iran	2019	Karimian
Studies have shown that three-dimensional vision, flexible rotation of the instrument, reduction of surgeon hand vibration with the help of vibration filter, ease of surgery and the ability to create the required patterns are the characteristics of surgeon robots.	Review of studies	Review	Comparison of robotic technique with standard laparoscopy in abdominal and visceral surgeries	Iran	2017	Theoretical

Reporting the results

After reading the summary and full text of the articles related to the research topic, the desired information was extracted for writing. Information required for each study included author name, year, place, type of study, sampling method, data collection tool and results. Finally, the information obtained from the articles was categorized and finally reported in the full text of a review article.

There are many surgical robots or intelligent medical assistants in the field of medicine, but to conclude which of these robots is better, you must first assess the time and place conditions and services, because each of these robots in There is a field of activity and it must be admitted that they also have limitations (15, 16).

Robotic technology allows general surgeons to operate with great precision, and areas that are difficult or even impossible to reach by humans can be accessed using a robotic system. The robotic surgeon's arms can rotate up to 280 degrees. All this brings better results for the patient. Iranian specialists have succeeded in gaining the technical knowledge of this robot surgeon and the technical knowledge of the mechanism design process, hardware and software Robots have

also been achieved (17). The results of studies conducted in Iran in the field of robotic surgery are as follows.

The results of measuring and recording the time required to start the robot, ease of working with the robot, the quality of the robot in response to the surgeon's instructions, the accuracy of the robot movements, the ability of the robot to provide full image coverage, no shaking or shaking image, The indefatigability of the robot in prolonged surgeries, the absence of unwanted movements and the lack of errors in movements indicate the safety and efficiency of the robot and its satisfactory performance during surgeries. Although launching a robot requires time and initial work, the results show a reduction in total operation time in most cases. Smoothness of motion, stability and no image shake are among the advantages of the robot holding the laparoscope over the human hand, so this robot can be a good alternative for the person holding the camera.

Table 2. Another review about method on 2021

findings	Research tools	type of study	Title	Place	Year	the writer
Mitral valve robotic surgery is well possible through a limited surgical procedure Mortality around the operation seems very acceptable and possible Even lower than a sternotomy.	Review of studies	Review	Mitral valve robotic surgery: Methods and results in a 20year review	Australia	2021	Monati
Robotic head and neck surgery is now regularly used in specialized centers for head and neck surgery.	Review of studies	Review	Current Advances in Robotic Head and Neck Surgery	Germany	2021	Their boe
A review of studies showed that robotic surgery had better overall survival than non-robotic resection of oral squamous cell carcinoma, and	Review of studies	Review	Robotic surgery versus non-robotic resection of oral squamous cell	American	2021	Chilacula
this method is recommended.			carcinoma			

The process of industrialization of surgical robots in several developing countries, such as the United States, must be accompanied by the removal of technical barriers and increased international cooperation	Review of studies	Review	analyze 100Most Read About Robotic surgery versus open surgery	China	2021	Chow
Robotic systems are widely accepted in the U.S and in various surgical specialties.	Studies	Review	Robotics in Spine Surgery	American	2021	Farber
Robotic surgery in a rural head and neck center is a safe and appropriate treatment option and has very few side effects and this method is recommended.	questionnaire	Retrospective	Oral robotic surgery: a safe and effective tool for the head and neck Surgery	Australia	2021	Huang
Robotic surgical systems were divided into open / closed, image-based / imageless, and active / inactive / systems The main goal is to improve the accuracy of operations.	Descriptive	Descriptive	Robotics in Orthopedic Surgery: Why, What and How?	Belgium	2021	Innocent
Robotic spine surgery was introduced in 2004.	Descriptive	Descriptive	The evolution of robotic surgery in the spine	New York	2021	because
Robotic surgery is a good option for adult spinal deformity surgery.	Questionnaire	Akahort	Have robotic methods improved postoperative results?	New York	2021	Croll
Robotic surgery can significantly reduce blood loss, intraoperative complications, and length of hospital stay, but increase readmission and surgery time. Robotic surgery in the treatment of endometrial cancer showed better results.	Review of studies	Review	The effectiveness of robotic surgery for endometrial cancer		2021	Hafng
Robotic-assisted radical prostatectomy was less	Review of	Review	Clinical results of robotic	American	2021	Hala

<p>recurrent and had lower pain scores up to 6 weeks postoperatively compared to open radical prostatectomy. Compared to laparoscopic prostatectomy, robotic surgery improves urinary and .sexual function</p>	<p>studies</p>		<p>surgery compared to conventional surgical procedures (laparoscopic or open)</p>			
--	----------------	--	--	--	--	--

The next step will be to simplify work with the device by upgrading the software and conducting more clinical studies to evaluate robot performance comparisons (18). Studies have shown that three-dimensional vision, flexible rotation of the instrument, reduction of surgeon hand vibration with the help of vibration filter, ease of surgery and the ability to create the required patterns are the characteristics of surgeon robots. Also, in general, the volume of blood lost during surgery, the length of hospital stay, the amount of pain, followed by a reduction in the number of analgesic doses consumed in the postoperative ward and the time to return to a normal diet and normal activity compared to Laparoscopic procedure is reduced.

On the other hand, the results of research have shown that the duration of the operation by the robot and the cost of surgery is longer than the laparoscopic method. Discussion and Conclusion: Robot surgery is not necessarily more expensive than laparoscopic surgery. Evidence now suggests that robotic surgery has a permanent role to play in the future of surgery. Therefore, surgeons should be actively diligent in the development of robotic surgery and begin preliminary and randomized studies with high prognosis and quality in this field (19). The results showed that the use of robot traps in hip arthroplasty, in addition to providing more accurate 3D images for the surgeon to assess the depth and size of the acetabular cavity, reduces the risk of displacement or dislocation of the replaced joint. Reduces the risk of complications such as infection and site bleeding for the patient as well as readmission to the hospital. The results of studies show that robotic surgeries have effective applications as a minimally invasive method. Therefore, they can be gradually replaced by other surgical methods, but what is important is to pay attention to improving skills in the field of relevant new inventions, strengthening infrastructure and allocating sufficient money to be able to use advanced technologies in a desirable and efficient way. Used for the benefit of the patient and the surgeon and other members of the treatment team (20). It is true that the elimination of natural vibration of the surgeon's hand, reducing the possibility of infection and postoperative infections, the possibility of deeper vision of the operating field and creating small and delicate incisions instead of large incisions by microscopic robots are the advantages of using robotic surgery. However, it is possible to reduce the feeling of tissue specificity under the operation by the surgeon, reduce the speed of communication with equipment and monitors and the possibility of a twenty-five second delay on the monitors can also be considered as disadvantages of remote surgery. Remote surgery is performed by robots and advanced medical systems, but due to its cost and lack of strong technological and communication infrastructure, this method has not yet been properly transferred in developing countries and is limited to developed countries (21).

Limitation of tactile data Using graphic data It was thought that robotic surgery would be used more, but this did not happen. Reasons for this include lack of public awareness of the benefits of this method, patients' refusal to have robotic surgery and surgeons' desire for traditional surgery (22). A study showed that the use of viewfinders will be effective in reducing the cost, weight, dimensions of equipment and also simplifying some medical operations. It should be noted that the use of observers strongly depends on the type of operation used and not all of these methods are yet clinically applicable because there are many challenges in ensuring the performance and safety of these methods. However, the multidisciplinary nature of this subject provides a wide field for study and research (23). Robotic surgery has made slow progress due to cost and patent protection. But now we are seeing an increase in the number of new robotic surgery systems. Several systems are CE certified, while in the EU alone TransEnterix Senhence has received FDA approval, and several more are currently being tested, which will increase competition and reduce costs by approving these new robots. In the future, robotic surgery will be more common than manual surgery (24). A "driver's license" is seriously required for robotic surgery. Ideally, a certified training program is required to define a robotic surgeon and ensure a high level of work. And the training pyramid must start from the ground up, so that, with the effectiveness of the training, robotic surgery is safe for the patient and the surgeon (25). Robotic surgical systems were divided into open / closed, image-based / imageless, and active / inactive / systems. The main goal is to improve the accuracy of operations. It should be noted that regardless of the typology of the robotic system, the surgeon is responsible for planning and approving the use of the type of operation. Accurate and consistent execution of instructions is entrusted to robots. Every surgeon, when considering which robotic system to use, must correctly evaluate their differences.)26(

One of the most important issues in remote surgery is the touch feedback system. Although surgeon robots increase the surgeon's agility, less vibration of the surgeon's hand, and better vision, they reduce their ability to understand. Other disadvantages of robotic surgery include the possibility of a twenty-five-second delay on monitors. Depending on the doctor's condition, the delay between when the surgeon sees the knife moving and the incision is actually less than one-fifth of a second. It is performed and increases the probability of cutting in the wrong place and the risk of surgery and the cost of the required equipment (27). The amount of bleeding after robotic surgery is low and for severe bleeding, even if it is small, it requires embolization or tracheotomy to control the bleeding. Large tumors, preoperative anticoagulant use, and a history of previous radiation are associated with an increased risk of bleeding after robotic surgery (28). In comparison with immediate and longterm results, no difference was observed in the duration of the operation, the number of times the blood transfusion was required, and the occurrence of severe postoperative complications. Compared to traditional surgical methods, robotic surgery reduces the number and severity of postoperative complications and improves treatment outcomes (29). In a study in the robotic surgery group, the rate of blood loss, length of hospital stay, and complications were lower, but the mean time of operation was longer compared to open surgery (30). Operating times for robotic surgery are time consuming due to the connection and stabilization of the instrument. The results of 260 cases of robotic surgery showed no increase in postoperative death (31). Over time, experience and innovation in platform design (Da Vinci), operating time is likely to decrease further (33, 32). However, a study showed that the benefits of robotic surgery have yet to be explored. Although the initial results are promising.)34(Also, in studies conducted in other countries regarding robotic

surgery as follows. One study found no major complications during surgery. Kidney surgery with the help of robots by experienced robotic surgeons is a safe and repeatable surgery in selected cases and the result is excellent connective tissue function. The use of robotic technology can provide low complication rates, rapid recovery, and better connective tissue function)³⁵ (. Robotics in spine surgery is an emerging technology that promises future plans. The accuracy of surgery in instruments implanted using robotics seems to be high. However, the effect of robotics on radiation levels is unclear and seems to depend on the technique and type of robot (36). Robotic surgery greatly affects spinal surgery and is still safer and more efficient. Finally, it offers a better 3D image (37). Robotic spine surgery was introduced in 2004. Robotic spine surgery has made great strides. This surgery is a reliable and accurate tool for spine surgery and has grown rapidly in recent decades and is still on the path of development and progress (38). Artificial intelligence has tremendous potential to revolutionize the comprehensive care of the spine. . It can assist surgeons in selecting preoperative patients, surgical symptoms, and improving individual postoperative care. Robotic surgery, while still in its infancy, has a very clear vision for robotic spine surgery. Robotic surgery can reduce surgeon fatigue and improve surgeon technical accuracy (39). Robotic systems are widely accepted in the United States and in various surgical specialties. This innovative technology is still relevant in the field of spine surgery. These systems have potential benefits such as increased screw placement accuracy, reduced operating time and reduced radiation. However, the various technical factors of these systems are constantly being re-evaluated to improve performance and achieve these goals (40). Robotic surgery is also very effective in adult spinal deformity surgery.)⁴¹(

Robotic hip arthroplasty was associated with a reduced length of hospital stay and reduced costs compared to conventional methods. However, robotic surgery was associated with readmission and the need for more blood transfusions.)⁴²(

Robotic surgery is an innovation in thyroid surgery that compensates for the disadvantages of conventional endoscopy. Robotic surgery has many advantages, including 3D imaging, motion scaling, and vibration elimination. Although robotic thyroid surgery is often associated with longer operating times than conventional open surgery, more robotic techniques are safer. Robotic surgery compared to conventional open surgery or endoscopy. It is associated with several benefits such as quality of life, aesthetic results, reduction of neck pain and sensory changes and reduction of discomfort in swallowing after surgery. According to surgeons, robotic surgery improves the patient's ergonomics. The time and cost of surgery in robotic surgery has been longer. Patient mortality was not different. The benefits of robotic thyroid surgery With conventional surgery, it is shown that robotic surgery can be an advanced surgical option for thyroid disease. Robotic thyroid surgery should be further developed as a surgical procedure for endocrinology, and head and neck surgeons have received this training, and robotic thyroid surgery is a surgical option.)⁴³(

Robotic surgery for the treatment of rectal cancer appears to be oncologically safe and appears to be better in terms of short-term complications and pathological quality indicators. The potential and proven benefits of robotic surgery should be considered. The benefits of robotic surgery for rectal cancer include improved three-dimensional vision, ease of use of the tool, improved surgeon ergonomics, and better access to narrow spaces such as the pelvis. However, studies have clearly shown the value of robotic surgery for patients and surgeons and need further studies.)⁴⁴(

Mesorectal robotics is a safe and sufficient technology for the treatment of rectal cancer and helps to maintain better urinary and sexual functions. Robotic surgery due to better wrist movements and better use of tools that facilitate autopsy, especially in narrow spaces, and facilitates the operation by minimizing damage to the surrounding tissues as well as due to the magnified view.)45(

Robotic surgery seems to be an effective method in terms of oncological and functional results and is effective in patient survival and its use is recommended in tumor staging and HPV status.)46(

Robotic-assisted radical prostatectomy was less recurrent and had lower pain scores up to 6 weeks postoperatively compared to open radical prostatectomy. Compared to laparoscopic prostatectomy, robotic surgery improves urinary and sexual function. Robotic surgery had fewer complications for endometrial cancer than laparoscopy.)47(

Mitral valve robotic surgery is well possible through a limited surgical procedure. Mortality around surgery seems very acceptable and possible. It is even lower than sternotomy. The rate of stroke was higher than sternotomy in the early stages of mitral valve robotic surgery, but now appears to be at least the same. After robotic surgery, 1 in 4 people needed a blood transfusion. The rate of renal failure around surgery is low. One in 200 patients develops a wound infection. The length of hospital stay did not decrease. Due to the huge level of innovation in mitral valve robotic surgery, this method seems very satisfactory.)48(

Robotic head and neck surgery is now regularly used in specialized centers for head and neck surgery. It is used in simple surgeries and easily accessible anatomical areas such as the mouth and throat. Disadvantages of this method include increasing the time required for the operation and increasing costs. For basal cranial, nasopharyngeal, or laryngeal surgery in patients with difficult anatomical conditions, systems with special surgical instruments for head and neck surgery should be developed. Despite the obstacles, we strongly believe that robotic systems will have a major impact on how we perform head and neck surgery over the next decade. Robotic head and neck surgery is recommended for better surgery in difficult areas, to reduce surgical complications, and to increase patient safety.)49(

Robotic surgery in a rural head and neck center is a safe and appropriate treatment option and has very few side effects and this method is recommended.)50(

A review of studies showed that robotic surgery has a better overall survival than non-robotic resection of oral squamous cell carcinoma, and this method is recommended.)51(

The number of female robotic surgeries has increased dramatically since the introduction of robotic surgery systems in Korea. Based on these data, it is expected that the continuous use of robotic surgery is widely used for both benign and malignant types of gynecological diseases. Many traditional surgeries are expected to be replaced by robotic surgeries.)52(A study on the application of robotic surgery in gynecological diseases showed that robotic surgery can significantly reduce blood loss, intraoperative complications, length of hospital stay, but the rate of readmission and operation time increasing. Robotic surgery has shown better results in the treatment of endometrial cancer.)53(

The robotic system has overcome some of the shortcomings of laparoscopy, including threedimensional vision limitation and hand tremor. Therefore, robotic surgery has taken many steps towards further progress in the field of general surgery. Although the safety and effectiveness of robotic surgery systems have been confirmed in most methods, in some methods robotic surgery has not been widely performed and is limited to a few highly

specialized centers. Robotic surgery in hepatectomy, gastrectomy, esophageal surgery, colectomy and pancreatectomy is performed unequally in the world, which may be related to the economic power of countries and the preference of surgeons, with the gradual reduction of the cost of robotic surgery systems and its standardization, we believe that robotic surgery will become gold and will become a standard method in general surgery, including surgical procedures as well as health insurance coverage.)54(

The operating time for robotic surgery was 30% longer compared to laparoscopy. The rate of re-admission to robotic surgery is higher. Compared to laparoscopic patients, robotic surgery patients were hospitalized longer. There was no evidence of improved robotic surgery performance over surgery or clinical outcomes.)55(

The rate of robotic segmentectomy has increased, and according to our study in robotic surgery, the operation time was longer, the blood loss rate was lower, and the hospital stay time was shorter. Our results show that robotic surgery can facilitate the function of complex anatomical parts.)56(

Robotic surgery has become the preferred method for abdominal surgery. Robotic surgery is recommended when vaginal surgery is not possible. So far, gynecological robotic surgery has shown better safety and clinical results than laparoscopy. Robotics has been developed to overcome laparoscopic challenges and has led to technological benefits such as improved ergonomics, 3D visualization capabilities, skill and range of motion with the tool joint, and elimination of hand vibration. To date, robotic applications in benign obstetrics and gynecology include hysterectomy, myomectomy, endometriosis surgery, sacrocolpopexy, adnexal surgery, tube reanastomosis, and cerclage. Robotic surgery may offer greater benefits than other methods in the obese patient population and in more complex cases. Advances in robotic technology, such as telemedicine surgery, could revolutionize gynecological surgery. Finally, this robotic device is an additional minimally invasive surgical instrument that can help minimize laparotomy in women.)57(

The use of robotic substrates in liver and bile duct surgery is growing rapidly. There is evidence that robotic surgery results are good. Robotic surgery is useful for managing complex cases such as iatrogenic bile duct injury, hepatic autopsy, or complex autopsy due to difficult anatomical positions. We believe that, for selected patients, robotic surgery should be part of the treatment of complex liver surgeries.)58(

According to studies, there is still room for development of robotic surgery. Lack of close cooperation between scientists, institutions and countries may have affected this issue. The process of industrialization of surgical robots in several developing countries, such as the United States, must be accompanied by the removal of technical barriers and increased international cooperation and exchange. Removing barriers and developing global surgical relationships should seize the opportunity to improve the situation.)59(

On the other hand, there is considerable variation in US hospital accreditation policies. However, the purpose of performing performance appraisals and monitoring is to improve patient outcomes. Extensive development and implementation of validation guidelines is recommended to optimize patient safety and outcomes (60). The subject of training in robotic surgery is also very important. The study showed that lack of technical skills affects the results of robotic surgery. Therefore, physician education is very important (61). The use of a standard curriculum for robotic surgery remains unclear. The choice of training methods and evaluation tools should be based on validity and application based on performance data. Clinical education

seems to simulate effective education (62). Also, in studies, the lack of clarity in the roles and responsibilities of nurses in robotic surgery and the lack of coordination for working conditions cause professional dissatisfaction and dismissal in nurses (63), which should also be considered.

Conclusion

Robotic surgery is one of the new and diverse technologies that the medical community at the national and international level will have to use and enter this path. According to research, the results showed that robots can not be used in any way and relied only on manpower, because manpower, ie the same surgeons have mistakes, so these robots can not be left out. Among the benefits of robotic surgery can be; Reduction of long recovery period after surgery, reduction of postoperative pain, reduction of the possibility of postoperative infection, reduction of hospitalization time, no need to break the sternum and open the chest in open surgeries, rapid healing of wounds, in The availability of certified surgeons with unique capabilities in more locations, greater accuracy, elimination of surgeon hand vibration, continuous and 24-hour operation 24 hours a day without fatigue. In addition to having many advantages, according to robotic surgery studies, it has disadvantages such as; Increasing the distance between doctor and patient, reducing the speed of communication with equipment and monitors, increasing the possibility of cutting the wrong place, the possibility of disconnecting the surgeon from the operating room, low network security and the possibility of hacking communication, patients' reluctance to use this equipment and technology, The robots are expensive, the doctor does not have an assistant, and the doctor does not have a sensory understanding of the patient's environment. It must be adapted to other technologies and used to serve the people. Although we are facing the development of surgical robots around the world, a review of scientific products in the field of surgical robots shows that the United States, China, and Japan are the three leading countries in this field, respectively, and Iran is in 15th place. The trend of scientific production in this field has started since 1990 and has been moving forward with a gentle slope and has gone through an upward trend since 2001. This trend has continued upward with fluctuations in different years. The results indicate that. There are few scientific developments in this field and few countries, universities, authors and publications have addressed this issue (13). Available worldwide.

References

1. Work in the operating room and recovery. Respected. R. Ghobraei, Tehran. Sotoudeh Publishing
2. Wall J, Chandra V and Krummel T. Robotics in general surgery, Medical Robotics, VanjaBozovic (Ed.), In Tech. 2008; ISBN: 978-3-902613-18-9, Available from: http://www.intechopen.com/books/medical_robotics/robotics_in_general_surgery.
3. Satava R.M. How the future of surgery is changing: robotics, telesurgery, surgical simulators and other advanced technologies. 2006.
4. Okamura A.M., Verner L.N., et al. Haptics for RobotAssisted Minimally Invasive Surgery. Robotics Research, M. Kaneko and Y. Nakamura (Eds.). Springer. 2010; pp361-372

5. Hamed A, Tang S, et al. Advances in haptics, tactile sensing, and manipulation for robot-assisted minimally invasive surgery, noninvasive surgery, and diagnosis. *Journal of Robotics*. 2012; Article ID 412816, 14 pages
6. 8. Smart assistants in medicine) Robotic surgery (Soraya Gharavi, Fatemeh Bashtani 1 - School of Computer and Electrical Engineering, Instructor, Esfarayen Higher Education Complex, Iran, North Khorasan, Esfarayen
7. Robotic Surgery: A Development in Modern Surgical Techniques: Mitra Zandieh, *Journal of Comprehensive Nursing and Midwifery* »Spring and Summer 2009 Issue 61
8. Application of robotics in medical industry, especially focus on surgery: A review study 2, Shideh Gorji * 2017
9. . Dubois F, Icard P, Berthelot G, Levard H (1990) Coelioscopic cholecystectomy. *Ann Surg* 211: 60-62
10. Dynamic Modeling and Identification of ARAS-Diamond: A Vitreoretinal Eye Surgery Robot. ISSN: 2476-6909; *Modares Mechanical Engineering*. 2021;21(11):783-795.
11. Robotic surgery, a big step in modern surgery. Seyed Mohammad Amin Mohajeri. 2019
12. . Gaskin TA, Ische JH, Matthews JL, Winchester SB, Smith RJ (1991) Laparoscopy and the general surgeon. *Surg Clin North Am* 71: 1085-1097.
13. Kalk H (1929) Erfahrungen mit der lapprskopie (Zugleich mit Beschreibung eines neuen Instrumentes). *Z Klin Med* 111: 303-348.
14. 4. Ruddick JC (1934) Peritoneoscopy. *West J Surg* 42: 392-405.
.18 Clinical evaluation of a new robot holding a camera in laparoscopic surgery - Preliminary results - Karimian - 2010
15. Investigating the advantages and disadvantages of using remote surgery method for implementation in Iran. Mohammad Javad Heidari Zahra Goli Seyed Mahyar Azimi Soda Ebadati Kahjoog. 2018
16. . Application of observers in medical operations with the help of robots. Fallahi. Tavakoli. Fifth year / No. 9 / Summer 2018
17. Duchalais E, Machairas N, Kelley SR, Landmann RG, Merchea A, Colibaseanu DT, et al. Does prolonged operative time impact postoperative morbidity in patients undergoing robotic-assisted rectal resection for cancer? *Surg Endosc*. 2018/03/17. Division of Colon and Rectal Surgery, Mayo Clinic, 200 First Street SW, Rochester, MN, 55905, USA. Division of Colon & Rectal Surgery, Mayo Clinic, 4500 San Pablo Road, Jacksonville, FL, 32224, USA. Division of Colon and Rectal Surgery, Mayo Clinic, 200 F; 2018; Available from
18. orelli L, Di Franco G, Guadagni S, Rossi L, Palmeri M, Furbetta N, et al. Robot-assisted total mesorectal excision for rectal cancer: case-matched comparison of short-term surgical and functional outcomes between the da Vinci Xi and Si. *Surg Endosc*. 2018;32(2):589–600.
19. Breda A, et al. Robot-assisted Kidney Transplantation: The European Experience. *Eur Urol* (2017), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2017.08.028>
20. Impact of Robotic Assisted Surgery on Outcomes in Total Hip Arthroplasty Ethan A. Remily, DO, Austin Nabet, DO, Oliver C. Sax, DO, MS, Scott J. Douglas, MD. 9 (2021) 46e49
21. Robotic Surgery for Thyroid Disease Jandee Lee a WoongYoun Chung b
22. Minimally Invasive and Robotic Mitral Valve Surgery: Methods and Outcomes in a 20-Year Review Johannes Bonatti^{1,2}, MD, Ingo Crailsheim^{1,2}, MD, Martin Grabenwöger^{1,2,3}, MD. 2021. DOI: 10.1177/15569845211012389

23. Current Advances in Robotics for Head and Neck Surgery—A Systematic Review Felix Boehm 1,2,* , Rene Graesslin 1,2, Marie-Nicole Theodoraki 1,2, Leon Schild
24. Transoral robotic surgery versus nonrobotic resection of oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma Yeshwant Chillakuru MSc | Daniel A. Benito MD | David Strum MD. DOI: 10.1002/hed.26724.2021.2021
25. Trends in robotic surgery in Korean gynecology Seungmee Lee1 ,Mee-Ran Kim2 , Seok Ju Seong3 , Jiheum Paek4 , Yoon Soon Lee5 , Eun Ji Nam6 , Yong-Man Kim7 , Young-Han Park8 , Tae-Joong Kim9 , Yong Beom Kim10, Tae Jin Kim11, San-hui Lee12, Chul Jung Kim13, Kyung-Do Ki1. <https://doi.org/10.36637/grs.2020.00059> Gyne Robot Surg 2020;1(2):50-56
26. Worldwide difusion of robotic approach in general surgery Rong Liu1 · Qu Liu1 · Zizheng Wang1 Received: 25 June 2020 / Accepted: 26 October 2020
27. The Longitudinal Efficiency of Robotic Surgery: an MBSAQIP Propensity Matched 4-Year Comparison of Robotic and Laparoscopic Bariatric Surgery Mark Dudash1 & Jason Kuhn1 & James Dove1 & Marcus Fluck1 & Ryan Horsley1 & Jon Gabrielsen1 & Mustapha Daouadi1. pringerScience+Business Media, LLC, part of Springer Nature 2020
28. Robotic Surgery of the Liver and Biliary Tract Francesco Guerra, MD, Michele Di Marino, MD, and Andrea Coratti, MD2018.. DOI: 10.1089/lap.2017.0628
29. Novel training methods for robotic surgery Andrew J. Sun, Monish Aron, Andrew J. Hung. Indian Journal of Urology, Jul-Sep 2014, Vol 30, Issue 3 333
30. The process of nurse adaptation to robotic surgery: A qualitative study Yasemin Uslu1 | Yasemin Altınbaş 2 | Tuğba Özercan3 | Meryem Yavuz van Giersbergen.2018